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**INDEPENDENTLY INSTALLABLE, SCALABLE,
AND FLEXIBLY USABLE COST-EFFECTIVE
MATERIAL FEEDING PRODUCT SERIES
DEVELOPMENT FOR BROWNFIELD
ENVIRONMENTS**

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1. Presentation of the Project

The main objective of our project is to develop an independently installable, scalable, and flexibly usable material feeding machine family, which can be cost-effectively utilized in brownfield environments.

Within the framework of the research, the engineering team conducted a comprehensive survey on CNC machines and robotic arms. Parameters of the feeding zone were defined. By leveraging parts designed and manufactured by selected machine manufacturing companies, we conducted product variance research to obtain appropriate parameters for the sizes and weights of parts to be manipulated. Research was conducted on machine connection possibilities, multi-feeding options, and finally, the integration of the designed machine into an Industry 4.0 system.

As part of the development, a robot arm-based base module was created, which must be physically connected to the machine being served via a docking station, as well as electrically and software-wise. Serving modules were developed for the base machine, which are responsible for material feeding. The resulting products of the development include an automatic tray loader, a vibratory feeder, a 3D camera-equipped product-independent feeder, and an automatic tray filler. Full documentation for the base machine and all its serving modules was completed, covering manufacturing, assembly, and sales requirements. An independent installation methodology was developed, allowing our partners to commission the purchased machines with their own specialists. Industry 4.0 connectivity was also developed.

Tools needed for sales, such as proposal templates and brochures, were created. The products were showcased on our website, in various trade journals, and at exhibitions.

During the project, we succeeded in developing a product series that we hope our partners will use with satisfaction in their brownfield investments.

1.1. Description of the Research/Development Activities

Our primary goal is to develop a universal, modular machine-feeding product series that can adapt to the majority of potential feeding tasks in the market. Currently, there is no such universal machine-feeding system applicable to all machines. We aim to achieve our goals through scientific research in the following areas:

Scientific achievements include:

- Feed zone model and product variance (IK1)
- Plans for machine connection methods and preparations (IK2)
- Multi-feeding techniques and layout plans for multi-feeding zones (IK3)
- Integration into Industry 4.0 (IK4)

As technical achievements, we aim to produce the following based on the theoretical results mentioned above:

- Base machine (KF1-M)
- Additional modules (KF2-M)
- Machine manuals and related documentation
- Methodology for independent installation
- Tools to support sales

Additional tasks include:

- Construction and testing of the base module (KF1-T)
- Construction and testing of additional modules (KF2-T)
- Industry 4.0 ecosystem integration study (IK4-SF)
- Data transmission to the monitoring system (KF4-M)
- Parameterization of the monitoring system for ecosystem integration (KF4-SF)

1.1.1 Feed Zone Model and Product Variance Research (IK1)

The essence of the research is to physically survey our target customer group and determine the physical feeding parameters of the machines to be fed. During the research, we create a 3D model space where the selected and standardized feeding dimensions are available. The feeding machine group's parameters will later need to be optimized to serve this model space.

By considering the cumulative space of the feeding locations of numerous surveyed machines, we aim to achieve the 95th percentile, ensuring that our machines can serve 95% of the surveyed machines within our target group.

In product variance research, we survey the physical parameters of products made by selected companies and determine the dimensions our machines must handle. The companies selected for the survey are general-purpose machine builders, meaning they are not specialized in serving specific industrial sectors. Thus, we can survey product sizes that meet general manufacturing needs.

1.1.2 Machine Connection Methods and Preparation Plans (IK2)

The aim of this research is to develop a machine connection system that enables the successful integration of our modular serving machine family even with older machines used by prospective customers. Both physical and software connection possibilities must be examined and developed.

1.1.3 Multi-Feeding Techniques and Layout Plans for Multi-Feeding Zones (IK3)

Maximum cost-efficiency could be achieved if one feeding machine could serve multiple processing devices. This presents several challenges. We will pursue two directions, both based on the database of feeding zones created in Task IK1:

- The first approach involves placing the processing machines within a distance where the stationary feeding device can "reach" both.

- The second approach involves the feeding device moving between the processing machines.

Theoretical layout models for operational segments must be created for both multi-feeding scenarios, followed by decisions on the most feasible method in our case.

1.1.4 Industry 4.0 Framework (IK4)

The resulting equipment from the project will be part of the company's digital ecosystem. The project outcome must fulfill general Industry 4.0 expectations, such as:

- Incorporating real-time equipment data into decision-making (maintenance, scheduling) mechanisms.
- Direct utilization of real equipment data for product qualification and documentation.

Through the collected data, algorithm-based forecasting and intervention management can be realized, reducing downtime, minimizing maintenance time and costs, and increasing production efficiency, monitorability, and parameterization.

1.2. The Base Machine (KF1-M)

The flagship of the project is the development of a robot cell equipped with a six-axis Universal Robots robot, a changeover table, and preparation for receiving an automatic tray loader. Additionally, a receiving station for a vibratory feeder will be established on the base module, which can also flexibly accommodate bulk material feeding systems equipped with cameras and flexible vibration systems instead of the tray loader.

To ensure future expandability, the module will be equipped with electric quick connectors, allowing for quick and easy connection with expansion modules. The fundamental operation involves the operator filling the changeover table trays as a buffer, and the robotic arm serving the manufacturing cell by loading raw materials and unloading finished products. When modules are connected, the raw material will be taken from the modules, and finished products will be placed onto another module.

1.3. Additional Modules (KF2-M)

We plan additional modules that can sort raw materials arriving in any form (organized or bulk) and hand them over to the robotic arm in a position understandable for further manipulation.

1.3.1 Automatic Tray Loader

An automatic tray mechanism that provides the possibility for preparing a larger buffer, potentially for an entire shift, for organized incoming products. It feeds the products arriving on trays to the machine-feeding station. Due to its modular design, numerous options are available for feeding or removing trays. It can stack trays into pallets or feed individual trays after sorting from ready pallets.

1.3.2 Vibratory Feeder

Small parts arriving in bulk can be fed using a vibratory feeder, provided the products are vibratable and not highly variable in nature. The unit sorts the small, bulk-fed products into the correct position using a circular vibrator, aligns them into rows on a linear vibrating rail, and delivers them to the feeding location.

1.3.3 Intelligent, Fully Product-Independent Feeder System Equipped with a 3D Camera

This module is intended for feeding more complex or heavier parts that cannot be delivered through a vibratory feeder. After programming, this module can feed any raw material meeting the boundary conditions in cooperation with the robot.

2.3.4 Tray Filling Automaton

This module can connect to a machine producing semi-finished products or a semi-finished product feeder, filling buffer trays from it and automatically placing them into secondary modules, effectively operating the system entirely automatically.

The device transports parts between various processing machines, places raw materials directly into the machine or onto the machine-feeding tray, and removes finished products from the processing machine, placing them at storage or packaging points located even further away.

When combined with the control of processing machines, it ensures automated operation. Importantly, physical and software compatibility with processing machines not originally designed for this purpose is achievable, as well as connectivity with Industry 4.0 systems.

1.4. Related tasks

- Construction and testing of the base module (KF1-T)
- Construction and testing of additional modules (KF2-T)
- Industry 4.0 ecosystem integration study (IK4-SF)
- Data transmission to the monitoring system (KF4-M)
- Parameterization of the monitoring system for ecosystem integration (KF4-SF)

In summary, during the project, scientific achievements include the creation of a feed zone model, a database of retrofitting connections, and foundational layout models for multi-feeding. Technical results include the base and additional modules of the equipment corresponding to these theoretical results, their associated documentation, and tools supporting sales, such as brochures, proposal templates, and an introductory website.

2. Presentation of the Novelty of the End Product

From the perspective of physical compatibility, a major drawback of existing machine-feeding units on the market is that they are generally only compatible with specific machine types of a given manufacturer. This makes integration with other brands or older equipment either impossible or highly challenging. The novelty of our product family lies in its ability to connect to most manufacturing machines available on the market and even handle mixed machine parks.

We aim to target a market segment where manufacturers are highly cost-sensitive and prefer to retrofit their older machines, originally not designed for automated feeding and process control, with automated feeders and controllers. In terms of physical compatibility, additional innovations include easy expandability and the ability to relocate the system between different machines.

From a software control perspective, existing machine-feeding units are typically only available with the manufacturer's own control system, which is often incompatible with other brands of machine tools. Our innovation lies in solving electrical and software compatibility issues to connect with the widest range of machine tools possible.

Another novelty is the Industry 4.0 compatibility of our system. By upgrading machines to "smart" status, especially older machines, we enable process automation, monitoring, and energy management. This provides data-driven support for managerial decisions regarding optimal production configurations, machine selection, and usage (e.g., batch sizes, machine utilization rates).

Additional competitiveness and innovation come from lower production costs. By eliminating design elements and building a higher proportion of the system from commercial components, we aim to reduce manufacturing costs.

Summary of Innovations:

- Compatibility with both old and new CNC machines, even if they were not originally designed for automated feeding, both physically and software-wise.
- Easy, modular expandability.
- Ability to assemble a feeding system tailored to the specific task using modules.
- Brand-independent connectivity, suitable even for mixed-purpose and mixed-brand machine parks.
- Easy relocation between machines.
- Industry 4.0 compatibility, even for machines not originally designed for this purpose.
- Overall, the modular design and easy relocation make automating an existing production system more cost-effective.

3. Physical Structure of the Modular Machine

Our product series for serving machining centers is modular in design. It consists of a base module that manipulates raw materials using a robotic arm and various feeding modules connected as needed to supply materials to the machine tool. These modules reduce operator involvement and mitigate errors and delays caused by human fatigue and inattention. Some modules are dedicated to material feeding, while others can be used for transporting and storing finished products.

Figure 1: Physical connectivity of modules

The base module is equipped with three docking sides, each capable of connecting one module simultaneously. In the configuration shown in the figure, the upper dock connects the base module to the CNC machine being served, while the left side features modules for material feeding, and the right side includes modules suitable for transporting finished products. An operator position is also indicated, allowing the base module to deliver specific parts directly to the operator if needed.

Usability in serial production is enabled by automated operation and communication between modules and the CNC machine being served. Universality is achieved through the interchangeable modules. The feeding modules can be connected to the free docking ports of

the base module attached to the CNC machine, while modules suitable for transporting finished products can be connected to the remaining free docking ports of the base module.

Through its gate system, the base module can deliver finished products directly to the operator. This option is useful when all elements of a small batch need to be inspected, for sampling in large batches, or for automatic rejection of defective items.

Industry 4.0 compatibility is achieved by establishing communication between the serving unit and the enterprise resource planning (ERP) system, enabling automated production initiation, monitoring of processes, and energy consumption.

3.1. Example Integrations

3.1.1. Example 1: Laser Engraver Integration

The base module is connected to a laser engraver. Small products to be engraved are positioned correctly by the vibratory feeder module and arranged on a specialized tray (with a capacity of 90 units) by the robotic arm of the base module. The tray is then placed into the laser engraver. During the engraving process, the robotic arm fills another tray with products to be engraved. The tray with finished engraved products is delivered to the operator through the gate system, and the next filled tray is placed into the engraver.

Figure 2: Serving a laser engraver with a base module and vibratory feeder

3.1.2. Example 2: Laser Engraver with Automatic Tray Loader

In this example, the previously described laser engraver setup is supplemented with an automatic tray loader. Finished product trays are not delivered to the operator but placed onto the automatic tray loader, where they can be stacked onto a larger collection tray. When the collection tray is full, the automatic tray loader moves it aside, making space for the next empty collection tray. The filled collection trays are organized into stacks and delivered out. This solution allows the operator to be absent for longer periods, perform other productive tasks, or serve multiple machine groups simultaneously.

Figure 3: Laser engraver with an automatic tray loader for enhanced efficiency